

REFORM OF THE LEGAL SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

Abdullayeva Asila

Namangan State University, Master

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7839476>

Annotation: this scientific article describes in detail about the judicial and legal systems that are being carried out at the present time. As such, the rule of law has been brought.

Keywords: Rule of law, people's power, citizen, international document.

The rule of law is a principle directly related to the concepts of people's power and Human Rights. Because the power of the people is understood as the right of citizens to participate directly or indirectly in the decision-making process. In this sense, the laws that are an expression of the will of the people, passed by citizens through representatives elected to Parliament or by themselves directly by referendum, are the result of popular power, figuratively speaking, the fruit. Human rights and freedoms are introduced into life by means of laws, in fact, the ultimate goal of laws is also to protect a person, his rights and freedoms.

The justification of lawmaking as the main elements of the rule of law in international documents for legality, covering a transparent, accountability and democratic process; legal certainty; Prohibition of arbitrariness; openness of independent and impartial justice; as well as the establishment of judicial control over administrative documents; respect and non-discrimination of human rights and equality before the law.

The rule of law is the Constitution in the activities of all public authorities, the laws of which have a supreme legal force, their superiority over all other regulatory documents and instructions that the authorities issue. The rule of law is a principle that serves to ensure democracy and legislation in society. This principle is enshrined in Article 15 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the supremacy of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan is recognized without words. The state, its bodies, officials, public associations, Citizens Act in accordance with the Constitution and laws." The principle of the rule of Law first expressed the strict rule of law in all jobs of public life and, as noted above, in the unconditional obedience of all state bodies, officials and citizens to the Constitution and laws; secondly, realizing that social relations are regulated in a manner consistent with the interests of society, citizen and state, when an atmosphere of stability, security and legal order is established on the mamla-kat scale; thirdly, the Prevention of violations of law, as well as participants in legal relations, is manifested in the fulfillment of the legal basis of laws in order

The real introduction of the principle of separation of powers in the country is an important guarantee of ensuring the supremacy of the Constitution and laws in Uzbekistan. According to him, the links of the legislative, executive and judicial authorities operate in their constancy, within the competence established by law. In harmonizing the relationship between them, the Supreme Judge is the law.

In accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the president of the country is a guarantor of the observance of the rights and freedoms of citizens, the Constitution and laws (Article 93). The activities of the president in this regard are of significant political-legal importance. He opens the way for the full introduction into life of constitutional principles, rules enshrined in laws by his decrees, decisions, creates appropriate legal mechanisms. The fact that the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan received an order "on the organization of the study of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (January 4, 2001) was an important event aimed at raising the status and prestige of mining in society. Although the main purpose of the decree is to increase constitutional literacy, legal culture among the population, it ultimately provides a thorough basis for the veneration of the Constitution, its priority observance.

In the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on measures to ensure the legality of regulatory documents of ministries, state committees and departments"(October 9, 1997), the task of ensuring the compliance of departmental normative acts of a universal nature with the Constitution and laws is assigned to the Ministry of Justice and their state registration is required. Departmental regulatory documents that are not officially registered will not have legal force, they cannot be introduced into life. The role of prosecutorial supervision in ensuring the supremacy of the Constitution and laws is great. Within the framework of this task, the prosecutor's office will take measures to increase the responsibility of Ministries, Departments, Public Associations, enterprises, institutions and organizations that directly fulfill the implementation of certain laws, to prevent violations of the law, to eliminate its causes and conditions in a timely manner. When cases of gross violations of the law are identified, measures of administrative and criminal liability are used. In order to ensure the supremacy of the Constitution and laws in Uzbekistan, organizational and legal guarantees and legal mechanisms should be constantly improved and their effectiveness should be increased.

Constitutions have a law and an internal structure. The external structure of the Constitution describes its relationship with other sources of law, the totality of relations, its place and role in the legal system and its significance in the system of social and normative regulation in society.

The article reveals the prospects for the development of civil society in Uzbekistan and analyzes the problems of the development of legal consciousness and legal values in modern society, identifies important structural and material differences between law and law, which is one of the main components of law.

Therefore, special attention is paid to improving the quality of legal services in our country. The regulatory framework in this direction has been fully updated and government decisions have been made aimed at determining the status of a legal service. Along with the development of dozens of departmental regulatory legal acts in order to provide methodological assistance to this area and its development, practical activities are regularly organized by the justice authorities. In addition, at the Center for the professional development of lawyers under the Ministry of Justice, the qualifications of employees of the legal service are being improved. In our country, reforms are being carried out in stages aimed at ensuring the activities of state bodies and organizations, especially legal in the middle and lower reaches, as well as providing them with quality and professional legal services. In particular, the activities of centers providing legal services to territorial units of a

total of 23 state bodies and organizations as a test in Namangan city, Karshi and blessing districts were established in the system of the Ministry of Justice and showed its positive effect.

Organization of Centers for the provision of legal services in state organizations a number of advantages:

- About 40 in the Republic through the organization of legal service centers billion. budget funds in excess of sums will be economical;
- State bodies and organizations of Centers for the provision of legal services does not obey their leaders, they carry out full independent activities;
- As a result, legality and law in state bodies and organizations ensuring the priority of quality will reach a new level;
- Through the establishment of legal service centers, they are able to functions and tasks that do not apply are removed and assigned to the employees of the center it is ensured that the assigned tasks are performed efficiently;
- Legal service centers are organized in the presence of Justice Departments as it is being done, a study of the activities of district-level legal services, there is no need to check. Direct control arises.

References:

- 1.O'zbekiston Respublikasining Konstitutsiyasi. – T.: O'zbekiston, 2020.
- 2.Davlat tili haqida (yangi tahriri). O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni.– T.: O'zbekiston, 1997.
- 3.O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining qarori, 09.10.1997 yildagi 469-son. <https://lex.uz/docs/-582735>
- 4.Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). The Constitution is a Legal Guarantee for the Development of the Country and the Well-Being of Society. International Journal of Human Computing Studies, 3(2), 105-109.
- 5.Abdullaev, A. (2021, April). Prospective directions of civil society in uzbekistan. In International Scientific and Current Research Conferences (pp. 70-77).
- 6.Maqsudova, Gulbahor (2022). MAMLAKATIMIZDA ADOLAT VA QONUN USTUVORLIGI TARAQQIYOTNING ENG ASOSIY VA ZARUR SHARTI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2 (2), 979-983.